

Surface Texturing on Stainless Steel by Direct Laser Interference Lithography

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Abstract—A method for the surface texturing of well-designed and high controllable micro dimple structures on stainless steel by direct laser interference lithography (DLIL) is presented. The method offers its innovation that the micro circular dimple structures can be fabricated directly by controlling the process of three-beam laser interference. Different exposure durations have been studied to achieve the optimum value of the dimple diameter and density in order to reduce the friction coefficient of stainless steel. The dry sliding test of friction coefficients were performed by mechanical tester (UMT-TriboLab) under normal loads of 15 N. The results indicate that the micro circular dimple structures with the average dimple diameter of 4.2 μm and density of 23 percent have about 77% reduction of friction coefficient compared with untreated surfaces.

Keywords—micro circular dimple structure; direct laser interference lithography; friction coefficient

I. INTRODUCTION

As one of the most usually used high-chromium bearing steels, stainless steel has been widely used in mechanical and biomedical bearing components [1-2]. However, the damage of the stainless steel are mainly wear and deformation under the condition of service. Therefore, for the objective to guarantee good comprehensive mechanical properties and high dimensional stability, the stainless steel should have the advantages of high hardness and good wear resistance.

Surface texturing as a viable means to enhance the tribological behavior of mechanical components has attracted a great deal of attention in recent years [3-5]. The wear resistant textured surface is initially ensured by precise optimization of its geometrical features, but the influence of texture quality cannot be neglected. Therefore, a proper selection of fabrication methods appropriate for tribological applications is imperative. Various texturing techniques are developed including heat treatment [6], chemical based techniques [7-8], physical deposition methods [9-10] and laser texturing [11-14]. Among the existing manufacturing techniques, laser surface texturing as the most commonly used method, are suitable for forming all kinds of complex three-dimensional texture patterns on various materials such as steel [15] and titanium [16-17]. However, the beneficial effect of textured surfaces on mechanical contact performances depends on the

manufacturing precision. It will also be very useful to assess the impact of micro and nano textures on the tribological performance. DLIL has been applied for various materials including the stiff materials such as metal and alloy even some relative soft materials such as UHMWPE. Texture feature size and geometrical characteristics such as the shape, diameter and texture density can be well-designed and controlled through the DLIL technology which was shown both analytically and experimentally to reduce the friction coefficient of steels. With the achievements in functional micro textured surfaces of various materials [18-22], DLIL technology is being considered and evaluated for other tribological components in industrial applications. In this work, direct laser interference lithography is presented to fabricate well-designed and high controllable micro circular dimples on stainless steel by nanosecond laser. Compared with other methods, the one-step and maskless lithography technique is suitable for surface texturing to improve the tribological performance of bearing surfaces in mechanical components. DLIL shows its innovation as a high efficient, high controllable and high accurate way to improve the tribological performance of stainless steel.

II. PRINCIPLE

Micro dimple structures with specific feature sizes can be achieved by DLIL via controlling the process parameters such as the wavelength, azimuthal angles, polarization directions, incident angles, laser fluences and exposure durations. The three-beam interference can be described as the superposition of electric field vectors of three laser beams, and it can be expressed as

$$\vec{E} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \vec{E}_i = \sum_{i=1}^3 A_i \vec{p}_i \cos(k \vec{n}_i \cdot \vec{r}_i \pm 2\pi\omega t + \phi_i) \quad (1)$$

In the case of the TE-TE-TM mode under the experimental conditions of three-beam interference, the intensity distribution I can be written as

$$I = |\vec{E}|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 A_i \vec{p}_i \cdot A_j \vec{p}_j \cos[k(\vec{n}_i \cdot \vec{r}_i - \vec{n}_j \cdot \vec{r}_j)] \quad (2)$$

where $A_i (i=1,2,3)$ is the amplitude, $\vec{p}_i (i=1, 2, 3)$ is the unit polarization vector, $k=2\pi\lambda^{-1}$ is the wave number, and λ is the wavelength, $\vec{n}_i (i=1, 2, 3)$ is the position vector, and $\phi_i (i=1, 2, 3)$ is the phase constant. In the case of TE-TE-TM mode with the experimental conditions of this work, Eq. (2) can be simplified as

$$I = A^2 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 3 + \sqrt{3} \cos \theta \cdot \cos(k \sin \theta \cdot y) \\ -\sqrt{3} \cos \theta \cdot \cos \left[k \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \sin \theta \cdot y + \frac{3}{2} \sin \theta \cdot x \right) \right] \\ -\cos \left[k \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \sin \theta \cdot y - \frac{3}{2} \sin \theta \cdot x \right) \right] \end{array} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where θ is the incident angle, x and y are the coordinates and $A_1=A_2=A_3=A$.

Dimple textured structures with specific feature sizes and geometrical parameters can be achieved by DLIL. In this work, a three beam laser interference lithography system was employed to fabricate micro circular dimples on 40Cr steel.

Many theoretical modeling techniques and numerical methods on various texture parameters and geometries of surface texturing for tribological applications have been developed in recent years [23-25]. Different fundamental results are commonly used to predict the tribological performances of textured surfaces. Although promising results have been obtained, finding optimal texturing parameters is still challenging due to the large number of variables involved in specific applications. Additionally, the desirable surface textures highly depend on the type of contact and operating conditions in certain cases. Although some general guidelines exist, it has become clear that in most cases textures need to be designed for a specific application and given operating conditions. In this work, the well-designed pattern was simulated by MATLAB. Fig. 1 shows that the intensity distribution of three-beam laser interference is a periodic circular dimple pattern.

The dimple density of the interference pattern depends on the incident angles and the wavelength of the laser source. The polarization also has an effect on forming the interference patterns, pattern contrasts and periods in three-beam interference lithography [26]. The diameter of the dimple structure is a function of the laser fluence and exposure time during the fabrication process. The shape of the pattern depends on the number of beams and polarization directions.

Fig. 1. (a) two-dimensional and (b) three-dimensional patterns of three-beam direct laser interference lithography simulation results.

III. EXPERIMENT

The material in this research was 40Cr steel which is directly applied to high precision bearing components. As for the experiments, the high power nanosecond Nd:YAG laser with the wavelength of 1064 nm was used to setup the three-beam laser interference system, aiming to directly fabricate dimple micro and nano structures on 40Cr steel. The frequency of laser source is 10 HZ and the pulse duration is 7 ns. Two beamsplitters and three high-reflectivity mirrors were used to set up the system and the quarter-wave plates and polarizers were placed before the exposed sample to control the laser fluences and polarizations of three interference beams. All the experiments were conducted in the air.

The schematic of three-beam laser interference system is shown in Fig. 2. As shown in the system, the three interference beams are from the beamsplitters and high-reflectivity mirrors with the azimuthal angles of $\phi_1 = 0$ deg, $\phi_2 = 120$ deg and $\phi_3 = 240$ deg, and incident angles of 8 deg. In the case of the TE-TE-TM mode, $\theta_1 = \theta_2 = \theta_3 = \theta$, $\psi_1 = \psi_2 = 90$ deg and $\psi_3 = 0$ deg.

Fig. 2. Schematic of three-beam laser interference system.

The energy of each interference beam was measured by laser power and energy meter (Coherent LabMax-top, Santa Clara, California). The dry sliding test of friction coefficients was performed by mechanical tester (UMT-TriboLab). The ball-on-flat testing conditions were described in Table 1.

Table 1. The dry sliding test conditions.

Normal Load (N)	Velocity (mm/s)	Duration (s)	Testing Ball (mm)	Temperature (°C)
15	5	300	5	25

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The micro dimple structures were measured by SEM (FEI Quanta 250 FEG). Dry sliding friction tests of textured 40Cr steel surfaces were performed using UMT-TriboLab. The dimple period was $8.6 \mu\text{m}$ and the diameter was $4.2 \mu\text{m}$. The sliding speed, distance and test time during the friction tests were fixed in the experiments. The applied load was 15 N.

As the result of the high peak power of a nanosecond laser source, 40Cr steel and oxygen reacted at a high temperature during lithography. Fig. 3 shows the scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of the 40Cr steel surface after the lithography with the exposure durations of $T=40 \text{ s}$ and $T=90 \text{ s}$ and the laser fluence of 0.45 J/cm^2 . Micro circular dimple structures are formed obviously in Fig. 3 (a) and the average period and diameter of circular dimples are about $8.6 \mu\text{m}$ and $4.2 \mu\text{m}$. The average dimple density was 23 percent in the measurement. As shown in Fig. 3. (b), most of the micro dimple structures are destroyed and the texture ratio is increased.

The dimple density and dimple diameter are regarded as the critical parameters for the reduction of the friction coefficient. Dimple textured surfaces have the beneficial influence on trapping wear debris to decrease further wear in the related mechanisms for the bearing surfaces [27].

Fig. 3. (a) and (b) SEM images of the micro dimple structures with the laser exposure durations of $T=40 \text{ s}$ and 90 s .

The optimal values of area density obtained by theoretical models showed that the highest load carrying capacity was generated when the density exceeded 15%, the friction coefficient remained low until about 30% [28]. Nevertheless, the theoretical results were usually different to those achieved from experiments, which showed material dependence [27]. On the bearing area, stress concentration and deformation will occur, and influence the friction coefficient of the dimple textured surface significantly depending on the area density and the pattern features [29]. For this case while the structure was fabricated on the 40Cr steel such a stiff material, the stress concentration at the edges of circular dimple needs to be carefully considered that higher stress is generated on the edge perpendicular to the sliding direction. The higher dimple density means there are more high stressed areas, which definitely results in deformation and energy consumption, and finally causes a friction increase. In order to decrease the friction and wear in this work, micro dimples with the density of 23 percent and the diameter of $4.2 \mu\text{m}$ were desired and fabricated on 40Cr steel.

In the experiment, the laser fluences and exposure durations have a strong influence on the dimple diameter and depth. Since the threshold of 40Cr steel ablation determines the energy of single pulses to be used, impacts of different fluencies need to be studied. The parameters used in the experiment are shown in Table 2. When the laser fluences were 0.45 J/cm^2 and $T=40 \text{ s}$, the stable value of friction coefficient was 0.04, as described in Fig. 4. When the exposure duration was 90 s, the stable value of friction coefficient was 0.34,

which was close to the result of the untreated surfaces. The samples with the laser fluence of 0.45 J/cm^2 were selected to analyze the effect on the dimple diameter with different exposure durations because when the energy density exceeded a certain level, the structures were molten and destroyed.

Table 2. Different exposure durations on the result substrates.

Samples	Exposure durations (s)	Fluences (J/cm^2)	Conditions
1	40	0.45	Clean room
2	90	0.45	Clean room

Fig. 4 Variations of friction coefficients with the load of 15 N for the samples of untreated and exposure durations of $T=40$ s and 90 s.

In the experiment, the exposure duration T has a strong influence on the friction coefficient. The friction coefficient effects of different exposure durations were investigated under dry sliding conditions. The experimental results with different exposure durations are described in Fig. 4. The friction curves can be divided into two stages. In the initial stage representing the run-in period that the dynamic coefficient friction of the textured surface with $T=90$ s had a steep slope for the first 10s and the untreated surface had a slope lasted for the first 50s. Comparatively, the textured surface with $T=40$ s had a very short run-in period. Then the values maintained a relatively stable trend where the friction coefficients were stabilized. It is obvious that the textured sample with the dimple density of 23 percent presented the stabled friction coefficient value smaller than that of the untreated surface under the same conditions. The friction coefficients at the stable stage were observed to be nearly 0.36 and 0.04 for the untreated area and textured with direct laser interference lithography, respectively, indicating that the well-designed micro circular dimple structures with the diameter of $4.2 \mu\text{m}$ and the density of 23 percent have the positive effect of the friction reduction for 40Cr steel.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, well-designed micro circular dimple structures were fabricated by three-beam DLIL. Different exposure durations have been investigated to analyze the

optimum textures for the reduction of friction coefficient. The low friction coefficient 40Cr steel surfaces can be obtained by controlling the process parameters. This method offers its innovation as a high efficient, high controllable and high accurate way to improve the tribological performance of 40Cr steel.

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